

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or mild brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not always black in shade. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear could be found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. However, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six ft in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are a few of the best at climbing timber. Their comparatively smaller dimension and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb timber for protection, food, and even hibernation. The majority of their food plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Eating regimen: Their varied food plan offers them the ability to live in a big range of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They're the almost certainly bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear assaults in North America, with 46 per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their spread-out nature and lowered habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large construct, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the identify of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt younger mammals corresponding to elk and moose. Their shade varies from mild blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft long, and have a shoulder peak of 3. Three toes. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on massive mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than those found in the Rocky Mountains resulting from a richer food regimen. Annually there are 46 assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Identified for their aggressive habits, grizzlies are liable for probably the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Size: Kodiak bears are almost as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight ft long, and 4 ft tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight loss program: Their weight loss plan is just like mainland grizzly bears. However, attributable to more plentiful food sources, the islands can help a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to turn out to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a more advanced social construction which ends up in less conflict between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. As a result of their isolation, there is just one attack on humans every different yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss plan is generally made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 toes tall. They are a threatened species because of lack of habitat from local weather change. Regardless of their monumental dimension polar bears can be fast, maintaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Features: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps gained Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight loss plan: Their food plan consists mostly of animals, especially seals which they'll scent from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears will be extraordinarily harmful. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are uncommon as a result of remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream shade chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Simple to tame and infrequently common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered vulnerable. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Food regimen: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on

people are increasing as people encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They're considered one of the best bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered only in China. 99% of its diet is bamboo. In truth, the second particular person in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they are thought-about a weak species. □□ Size: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and may be over four ft tall, a formidable feat contemplating they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at start. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same sample in light brown and white. □□ Weight loss plan: Unlike other bears the panda's diet is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The giant panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo retains them common: they poop over forty times a day! □□ Dangerous? Assaults are uncommon but harmful, provided that pandas have considered one of the highest chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Solar bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however thought of weak and on the decline as a result of lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different body components used in traditional medicines. □□ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that looks like a rising sun. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Food regimen: Solar bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they've an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Harmful? On account of its shy nature, assaults are uncommon. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of less than 20,000, they are thought of susceptible. □□ Size: They are fifty five to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're straightforward to inform other than other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and may out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from bushes. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their big curved claws. □□ Food regimen: Their eating regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They're one of the vital aggressive bears, with essentially the most attacks on people, largely on account of shock encounters. They blow the mud around with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and don't mix effectively with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's last brief-confronted bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that seem like glasses. This vulnerable species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last brief-confronted bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Options: The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes look like glasses. They spend most of their time in timber where they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. □□ Weight loss program: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a eating regimen consisting of mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they will opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Harmful? Dwelling in remote mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear behavior is nearer to the polar bear. They function the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, just like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA checks were unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas aren't bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in house. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their very own family that are closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS. Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that will indicate

a bear is close by, during which case you need to be additional vigilant. Here are a number of ideas you need to use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies protected.

2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you might have great intentions, a bear is likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP).** In the event you see a bear, don't attempt to method or feed it. This contains meals, but also your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you choose, be certain it's a minimum of 200 toes away out of your tent so you don't attract bears to your campsite.
4. **Stay CALM.** In the event you meet a bear, don't run. Try to make your self look as large as possible, waving your arms above your head. You too can prolong a jacket above your head to make your self look bigger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Do not scream or try to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Speak to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and [large panda teddy](#) use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward.
6. **Fight Back.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play dead. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8. Zero to 8.4 ft long, and 4. Zero to 5.25 feet tall, the biggest bear by both measurement and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all of your power and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is essentially the most harmful? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for probably the most assaults. When in bear nation, it's at all times sensible to carry bear spray. It's nicely deserved, particularly when cubs are around. Each year there are approximately forty six grizzly attacks, 6 resulting in death. In North America, grizzly bears have essentially the most fearsome popularity. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most likely to see an American black bear, on average there is only one attack per 12 months. In terms of uncooked bite power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are sturdy and to not be messed with. When using the chunk pressure quotient (bite power relative to measurement), the sun bear packs essentially the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fire however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he grew to become an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous thru-hikers to try to grasp the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, although he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a accountability-free life-style. He also may be the primary bear to receive his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would go to on the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near where he was from. Chris additionally wrote How one can Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After through-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to supply fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

